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By

**Felix Chari
Bongani Muchanyuri
Macleans Mzumara**

Research Article

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***Felix Chari, Bongani Muchanyuri & Macleans Mzumara**

Department of Economics, Bindura University of Science Education, P/Bag 1020, Bindura, Zimbabwe.

*Corresponding Author's Email: charifelix93@gmail.com, Phone +263 775994001; +263 713271777

ABSTRACT

The authors investigated the comparative advantage of Ethiopia and the role played by international purchasing. They found that Ethiopia has 302 product lines in which it has revealed comparative advantage, RCA equal and greater than 1. The authors have concluded that Ethiopia has comparative advantage in 302 products. Tanned/crust skins of sheep/lambs were found to have a revealed comparative advantage index of 1821.51. International purchasing play a significant role in promoting comparative advantage.

Keywords: International trade, international purchasing, exports, revealed comparative advantage, Ethiopia.

INTRODUCTION

Comparative advantage provides a mechanism for a country to gain from international trade through specialization. It gives the country a competitive edge over other countries in the products in which it has comparative advantage. Unlike absolute advantage, every country may possess some sort of comparative advantage in some products it produces. International purchasing is linked to comparative advantage. A firm source its supplies from other countries other than domestically can significantly benefit if it sources its supplies from countries which have comparative advantage in their production. The gains for the firm would be in the form of low prices and efficient supply due to the country that export the products. This paper investigates the comparative advantage of Ethiopia and the role played by international purchasing concept. Ethiopia is a member of the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa hence it is one of the key players in trade in the region.

Background

Ethiopia is the member of African Union and the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa. It shares a common border with Eritrea in the North. On the Eastern side, it shares a border with Somalia. In the same geographical area like Somalia, it shares a border also with Djibouti. Ethiopia shares a common border with Kenya on its Southern part. Sudan is its neighbor in the West and South-West. Ethiopia has a population of 72.4 million with 200 dialects. The country basically depends on agriculture with estimated over 90% of its population solely dependent on agriculture mainly at subsistence level. Ethiopia carried out trade liberalization between 1974 and 2009. The reforms were at their peak from 1992 onwards. Trade liberalization brought in positive results in Ethiopia (Allaro, 2012).

Comparative Advantage

Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage states that specialization and free trade will bring gains to both countries engaging in international trade (real wages will increase) and that countries which may not be absolutely very efficient producers can also benefit due to comparative advantage. A country is in a position to enjoy comparative advantage in the production of a product when the said product can be produced with a lower expenditure in comparison with other products the country produces. It is argued that even though a nation may have an absolute advantage in the production of both products. Ricardo emphasized that specialization and trade have roles which provide mutual benefits. When nations specialize in the production of product in which they possess comparative advantage, they are likely to have optimum combined output and allocate their endowment very efficiently. A nation

possesses comparative advantage in the production of a particular product if its opportunity cost in terms of another product produced by another is lower (Case & Fair, 2002).

According to Case and Fair (2002), the Heckscher-Ohlin theorem explains that the source of comparative advantage comes from its factor endowments. That means a nation possess a comparative advantage in the production of a good if that nation is endowed with inputs used more intensively in the process of production of that good. According to Mzumara (2006), Hescheker-Ohlin theorem is an extension of the principle of comparative advantage and according to them; international differences in cost come as a result of differences in factor endowment. A country with an abundant endowment will export the product which uses its abundant factor most intensively and then it will import goods that use its scarce factor less intensively. However, it is factor endowment scarcity which gives rise to comparative advantage (Khatibi, 2008). This explanation is not correct when Mzumara (2006) and Widgren (2005) are taken into account. According to these two authors, they attribute comparative advantage from factor abundance. It is the factor abundance which gives rise to comparative advantage. They dispute Khatibi (2008) explanation which centers on scarcity rather than abundance as the source of comparative advantage. According to Kowalski (2011) comparative advantage moves along with policies and institutions. That is the differences in national policy settings and their performance lead to differences in productivity between countries leading to differences in gain from international trade. Further, comparative advantage arises due to the stage a country may be in the process of economic development. The author concludes that trade liberalization and comparative advantage led specialization does not limit economic development instead it engineers it. Goldin (1990) asserts that the principle of comparative advantage is the only proposition in social sciences which remain true and non-trivial. It has come to be accepted as universal law in international trade. A nation has comparative advantage in the production of a particular product if it is relatively well gifted with factors used to produce a particular product and such factors are used more intensively in the production of the said product.

INTERNATIONAL PURCHASING

According to Research and Market (2013), to succeed in the global economy is only feasible if a firm supply base is competitive globally. Firms which are successful source their supplies beyond their borders and they tend to establish relationships with reputable suppliers in foreign countries. This provides a link with comparative advantage. A country possesses comparative advantage through the production of its firms. That means firms from other countries will establish working relationship with firms in the country that has comparative advantage. Through comparative advantage, the purchasing firms can benefit by sourcing from such countries in terms of lower prices and efficient supply.

International purchasing does not operate in isolation. It ought to be integrated into firm's purchasing strategies. In essence, this calls for appropriate skills and know-how which often lack in such firms' buying departments. Success entails intra-firm linkages through purchasing, finance and other logistic factors mostly absent in firms wholly dependant on local supply chain. So basically, it is the firms which look beyond its borders to source its supplies which will succeed. Such success depends on selecting the right suppliers, in this case, countries which have comparative advantage in those supplies.

The globalization of markets, comparative advantage provided by some emerging nations and advancement in information technology as well as improvement in transport logistics has led nations to re-orient themselves with outward policies. International sourcing as well as international manufacturing has become part of essential strategic decisions the firms have to make. International sourcing and most specifically the location of parts of the value chain to other countries often has to overcome cultural barriers and unfamiliar business requirements (Nassimbeni & Sartor, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

The authors used the export data for Ethiopia and the export data for the world obtained from the International Trade Centre's TradeMap in Geneva Switzerland for the periods 2008, 2009 and 2010 to compute Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) index. Then an average RCA for the three periods for each product line was computed. According to Ferto and Hubbard (2000) RCA is a useful tool which helps in determining whether a country has comparative advantage or not. Richardson and Zhang (2001) have defined RCA as ratio of ratios which show relative trade shares. The technique was developed and used by Balassa (1965) in the form of:

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{w,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{w,tot}} \right)$$

With:

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports in the world.

An RCA of equal and greater than 1 demonstrates that the country has Revealed Comparative Advantage. In other words, the exporting country is relatively specialized in producing and exporting the product line. An RCA of less than 1 demonstrates that the country has no Revealed Comparative Advantage and is not specialized in the product line (Balassa, 1965; Krugell & Matthee, 2009).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethiopia has 302 product lines which have RCA equal or greater than 1. This shows that Ethiopia has revealed comparative advantage in those products. Ethiopia is therefore specialized in the production of such products. Table 1 below shows top 50 product lines with the highest RCA

Table 1: Top 50 product lines with highest RCA

Product code	Product description	RCA 2008	RCA 2009	RCA 2010	AVERAGE RCA
410530	Tanned/crust skins of sheep/lambs without wool on, in dry state	1607.68	1904.14	1952.694	1821.51
120740	Sesamum seeds	1314.68	1590.50	919.9517	1275.06
020450	Goat meat, fresh, chilled or frozen	1163.85	725.14	833.08	907.38
071350	Broad beans and horse beans dried or shelled	952.95	839.82	696.86	829.88
120799	Oil seeds and oleaginous fruits	900.0848	900.30	550.53	783.64
010619	Live animals	450.71	536.73	918.98	635.47
410621	Tanned/crust hides & skins of goats/kids without wool/hair on, in the dry	1599.62	81.67	0	560.43
070990	Vegetables, fresh or chilled	283.75	372.31	443.56	366.54
410221	Sheep or lamb skins, pickled without wool	970.65	116.70	0	362.45
060210	Cuttings and slips, not rooted	336.07	375.20	327.93	346.40
130190	Natural gum, resin, gum-resin, balsam, not gum arabic	261.05	319.5055	303.72	294.76
071320	Chickpeas, dried or shelled	417.42	198.94	260.84	292.40
140490	Vegetable products	862.18	0.04	0.01	287.41
090111	Coffee, not roasted, not decaffeinated	346.43	202.56	249.24	266.08
520300	Cotton, carded or combed	416.59	212.47	93.77	240.94
520528	Combed single cotton	73.24	611.96	25.14	236.78

071333	Kidney beans and white pea beans dried shelled	267.13	226.77	205.31	223.07
410622	Tanned/crust hides & skins of goat/kids without wool/hair on	101.27	369.754	108.25	193.09
521214	Woven cotton fabric, <200m ²	169.47	150.73	256.94	192.38
950310	Electric trains, train set	17.50	422.94	54.46	164.97
261590	Niobium, tantalum and vanadium ores and concentrates	43.62	26.52	419.94	163.36
152190	Bees wax, other insect waxes and spermaceti	193.35	157.09	98.97	149.80
091010	Ginger	106.93	122.77	197.24	142.31
410692	Tanned/crust hides & skin, without wool/hair on, in the dry state	26.32	249.96	78.35	118.21
070820	Beans, shelled or unshelled, fresh or chilled	180.35	91.78	51.58	107.91
071332	Beans, small red (Adzuki) dried, shelled	93.93	97.66	81.22	90.94
071390	Leguminous vegetable dried, shelled	31.87	14.71	177.27	74.61
020410	Lamb carcasses and half carcasses fresh or chilled	104.97	53.67	62.30	73.65
090930	Cumin seeds	72.59	70.19	75.14	72.64
410691	Tanned/crust hides & skins without wool/hair on, in the wet state	211.22	0	0	70.41
411200	Leather furth. Prepared after tanning/crusting, including parchment-dressed leather	64.58	65.86	74.33	68.25
130211	Opium sap	201.40	0	0	67.13
121010	Hop cone, not ground, powdered or pelleted and lupulin	18.254	82.35	99.02	66.54
091030	Turmeric	44.10	72.29	83.20	66.53
010611	Live primates	180.50	12.41	0	64.30
071340	Lentils dried, shelled	63.65	59.98	59.32	60.95
410229	Sheep or lamb skins, raw, except pickled, no wool	178.83	0	0	59.61
680410	Stones for milling, grinding or pilping	67.97	63.45	42.26	57.89
630319	Curtains drapes blinds valances, material, knit	75.65	89.42	6.24	57.10
010290	Bovine animals, live, except pure-bred breeding	44.62	50.22	75.52	56.79
610729	Men's, boys nightshirts or pajamas, of cotton	0	0	169.67	56.56

120890	Flour or meal of oil seed, fruit, except mustard, soy	104.49	51.80	10.37	55.55
411390	Leather furth. Prepared after tanning/crusting, including parchment-dressed leather	55.67	47.73	48.21	50.54
845929	Drilling machines for metal, except num controlled	0	33.92	114.41	49.44
261400	Titanium ores and concentrates	51.19	86.57	5.72	47.82
620829	Women's, girls nightdresses, pajama, material not knit	0	0	130.01	43.34
010410	Sheep, live	35.95	44.79	47.58	42.77
010690	Live animals	19.93	0	83.48	34.47
410510	Tanned/crust skins of sheep/lambs without wool on, in the wet state	85.20	15.58	0	33.59
520710	Cotton yarn (except sewing thread) >85% cotton, retail	0	34.36	65.12	33.16

Source: TradeMap (2013)

Tanned or crust skins of sheep or lambs tops the product list with the highest index of 1822. This product line is followed by sesamum seeds with an index of 1275. The third position is occupied by goat meat with an index of 907. It is followed by broad beans and horse beans with an index of 830. The fifth position is occupied by oil seeds and oleaginous fruits with an index of 784.

Basically most of the products in the top 50 are agricultural products. Animal meat and their by-products are also very prominent in Ethiopia. There is little manufacturing products amongst the top fifty. The manufactured products include: curtains drapes blinds valances; men's and boy's night shirts; women's and girl's night dresses and pajama; and drilling machines. However, most of the products that Ethiopia has comparative advantage in are products which fetch low values in the international market. Ethiopia is gaining from international trade as advocated by Ricardo that it is not absolute advantage which matters but it is comparative advantage which matters and a country will have certain products that it has comparative advantage in. In this case, Ethiopia has 302 product lines in which it has comparative advantage respectively. However, the number of the products is too small although Ethiopia is highly specialized in them as demonstrated by the indices. It is clear that Ethiopia should focus on the production of these products and then export them. Ethiopia should therefore import products in which it has no competency to produce them. In doing so Ethiopia will continue to specialize in them. A focused export promotion program can help to identify markets for these products.

Other countries which want to outsource from Ethiopia will have to target these products in which Ethiopia has demonstrated that it is capable of producing them and supplying them. Ethiopia has demonstrated as compared to other producers, it is very much competitive on these 302 product lines.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is concluded that Ethiopia has comparative advantage in the production of 302 product lines and is benefitting from engaging in international trade with other countries. However, its comparative advantage is limited to 302 product lines. The base of its comparative advantage is therefore very narrow. In Ethiopia, there is also very little manufacturing going on. It is recommended that Ethiopia should diversify and venture into high level manufacturing in order to gain more in international trade. This will help Ethiopia export high value products which will lead to higher earnings to be realized from international trade. International purchasing plays a significant role in promoting comparative advantage. It is recommended that countries should source their supplies from countries which have

comparative advantage in the production of such products. In case of Ethiopia, countries can source from amongst the 302 products in which Ethiopia has comparative advantage.

REFERENCES

- Allaro, H.B. (2012). The impact of trade liberalization on the Ethiopia's trade balance. *American Journal of Economics*, 2(5):75-81.
- Balassa, B. (1965). Trade liberalisation and revealed comparative advantage. *The Manchester school*, 33(2):99-123.
- Case, K & Fair, R. (2002). *Principles of Economics*. 6th Edition. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Business Publishing.
- Ferto I., & Hubbard L. J. (2000). Revealed Comparative Advantage and Comparative and Competitiveness in Hungarian Agri-Food Sectors. Institute of Economics Hungarian Academy of Sciences, New Series 2002/8
- Goldin, I. (1990). Comparative advantage: Theory and application to developing country agriculture. OECD Development Centre, Working paper no. 16.
- Khatibi, A. (2008). Kazakhstan's revealed Comparative Advantage Vis-à-vis the EU-27. ECIPE Working Paper no. 03/2008
- Krugell, W. & Matthee, M. (2009). Measuring the export capability of South African regions. *Development southern Africa*, 26(3):459-476.
- Mzumara, M. (2006). *The Theory of Money and Banking in Modern Times*. Mustang: Tate Publishing LCC.
- Nassimbeni, G & Sartor, M. (2006). International purchasing office in China. *Production Planning & Control*, 17(5): 494-507.
- Research & Market (2013). International purchasing selection, engaging and managing the world's best supplier. From www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/42716/international_purchasing_selecting_engaging. (Retrieved April 16, 2013).
- Trademap (2013).
- Richardson D. J., & Zhang, C. (1999). Revealing Comparative Advantage: Chaotic or Coherent Pattern Across Time and Sector and the US Trading Partner? National Bureau of Economic Research, Working Paper 7212. Trade statistics. From www.trademap.org (Retrieved April 1, 2013).
- Widgren, M. (2005). Revealed Comparative Advantage in the Market. Turku School of Economics, the Research Institute of Finish Economy (ETLA), CEPR and CESifo.